

New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Counterproposal Bipartite and Counteroffer Path By Counterargument Stable Sequence As Hyper Findings On Super Gatherings

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1 SYNOPSIS

In this scientific research, (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V'} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V'} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V'} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \min_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) | \\
 & \quad V_j \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'', \exists V_i \in V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) > (-/ : \text{NOT DEFINED}) \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) > (-/ : \text{NOT DEFINED}) \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) > (-/ : \text{NOT DEFINED}) \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad \text{then } V_j \in V'', \text{ until } V'' = V_{NSHG}\}
 \end{aligned}$$

In this scientific research, new configurations are introduced for the new SuperHyperNotions, namely a Stable Sequence and a Neutrosophic Stable Sequence. Two different SuperHyperDefinitions were started for them, but research has progressed and SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperUniform, and SuperHyperClass are well-defined and well-reviewed based on them. Literature review is implemented throughout this research. To shine the light and importance of this research, a comparison between this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions and basic SuperHyperNumbers is presented. Definitions are followed by examples and examples, so clarifications are guided by various tools. Applications are designed to understand the theoretical aspect of this ongoing research. “Cancer diagnosis” are the things that are being researched to explore the challenges that make sense in ongoing research and future research. It is a special case. Cells are viewed in the intended manner. There are different types of them. Some are individual and some are well modeled by groups of cells. All these types are officially called “SuperHyperVertex”, but the relationships between them all are officially called “SuperHyperEdge”. “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” frameworks are selected and selected for research on “Cancer Diagnosis”. Thus, these complex and dense super-hypermodels open avenues for research on theoretical aspects and “cancer diagnosis”. Ways to pursue this scientific research have been considered. It has also been formally collected in the form of several

questions and problems. It is useful to define a “neutrosophic” version of Stable Sequence. Since there are more ways to get type results a Stable Sequence becomes more understandable. In order to master the Neutrosophic Stable Sequence, there is a need to “re-define” the concept of “Stable Sequence mastery”. SuperHyperVertices and SuperHyperEdges are assigned by alphabetical labels. In this method, the position of tags is used to assign values. Suppose a Stable Sequence. If the specified table contains “values of vertices, supervertices, edges, hyperedges, and hyperedges belonging to Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” with key points, it is redefined. ” values of vertices & number of positions in alphabet”, ”Values of SuperVertices&maximum values of its vertices”, ”values of edges&maximum values of its vertices”, ”super edge values&max values of its vertices”, “super edge values” and maximum values of its endpoints”. To get examples and structural examples, I would like to introduce the next SuperHyperClass SuperHyperGraph based on Stable Sequence. This is the original. Having the foundation of the previous definition in the SuperHyperClass type would be disciplined. If there is a need to have all Stable Sequence until Stable Sequence, then it is officially called “Stable Sequence”, but otherwise, it is not Stable Sequence. There is some explanation for the original definition titled “Stable Sequence”. These two examples are further explored and distinguished because they are characterized in the SuperHyperClass disciplinary methods based on a dominant Stable Sequence. Because of having Stable Sequence, there is a need to “re-define” the concept of “neutrosophic Stable Sequence” and “neutrosophic Stable Sequence”. SuperHyperVertices and SuperHyperEdges are assigned by alphabetical labels. In this method, the position of tags is used to assign values. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” is redefined if the desired table exists. And if the desired table exists, a Stable Sequence is redefined to a “Neutrosophic Stable Sequence”. It is useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there are more ways to obtain Neutrosophic type results, a SuperHyper- Neutrosophic Stable Sequence becomes more understandable. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. If the desired table exists, there are a number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. So are SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite and SuperHyperWheel. ”Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel”. A graph is SuperHyperUniform if it is a SuperHyperGraph and the number of SuperHyperEdges elements is the same. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are a number of SuperHyperClasses as follows. It is a SuperHyperPath if there is only one SuperVertex as an intersection between two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions. If only one SuperVertex is given as an intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, it is SuperHyperCycle. It is SuperHyperStar and only one SuperVertex as intersection among all SuperHyperEdges. It is SuperHyperBipartite, and only one SuperVertex is given as the intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, and these SuperVertices, which form two distinct sets, have no SuperHyperEdge in common. This is SuperHyperMultiPartite. Only one SuperVertex is given as an intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, and these SuperVertices, which form separate multisets, have no SuperHyperEdge in common. If only one SuperHyperEdge among the given two SuperHyperEdges is a SuperHyperWheel and a SuperVertex has a SuperHyperEdge with any regular SuperVertex. SuperHyperModel suggests specific designs and specific architectures. SuperHyperModel is officially called “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. In this SuperHyperModel, the “special” cells and the “special group” of cells are SuperHyperModeled as “SuperHyperVertices” and the common and desired properties between the “special” cells and the “special group” of cells. SuperHyperModeled as “SuperHyperEdges”. Sometimes, to have a more accurate SuperHyperModel, it is useful to have some degree

of determinism, uncertainty, and neutrality, in this case the SuperHyperModel is called “Neutrosophic”. In future scientific research, the foundation will be based on “diagnosis of cancer” and the results and definitions will be introduced in redeemed methods. Cancer diagnosis in long-term practice. The specific region is assigned by the model (called SuperHyperGraph) and the long cycle of movement of the cancer is determined by this scientific research. Sometimes the movement of cancer is not easy to detect, because there is certainty, uncertainty and neutrality about the movements and effects of cancer on that area. This event leads us to choose another model [which is said to be the Neutrosophic superhypergraph] in order to have a proper understanding of what happened and was done. There are some specific models, which are well known and have names, and some SuperHyperGeneral SuperHyperModels. The movements and effects of cancer in complex pathways and between complex groups of cells can be visualized with a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (-/SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The goal is to find the longest Stable Sequence or the strongest Stable Sequence in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. Some general results are presented for the longest Stable Sequence called Stable Sequence and the strongest Stable Sequence called Neutrosophic Stable Sequence. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges, but it is not enough as having at least three SuperHyperEdges is necessary to form any style of cycle. There is no form of any cycle, but literally, it is the transformation of any cycle. It literally transforms and does not form. A basic introduction to the theory of Stable Sequence Neutrosophic, SuperHyperGraphs and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs is suggested.

Keywords: Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, SuperHyper_{Stable Sequence}, Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition

AMS Subject Classification: 05C17, 05C22, 05E45

2 Applied Notions Under The Scrutiny Of The Motivation Of This Scientific Research

In this scientific research, there are ideas in the prominent frameworks of motivations. I try to bring motivations in narrative ways. Some Cells have faced attacks from the established situation with cancer attacks in this case, there is some analysis embedded in the case current situations where cells can be labeled as some groups and some groups or individuals are overlabeled, all from behaviors to overcome cancer attacks. In embedded situations, cell individuals and cell groups can be considered as “new groups”. So it encourages us to find suitable SuperHyperModels for more appropriate analysis about this dirty story. I found SuperHyperModels, officially called “SuperHyperGraphs” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. In this SuperHyperModel, cells and groups of cells are defined as “SuperHyperVertices” and relationships between individual cells and groups of cells are defined as “SuperHyperEdges”. So this is another motivation for us to do research on this SuperHyperModel based on “cancer diagnosis”. Sometimes, things get worse. The situation has passed certainty and precise style. So it is beyond them. There are three descriptions, i.e., degrees of determination, uncertainty, and neutrality, for any object based on ambiguous forms, i.e., incomplete data, imprecise data, and uncertain analysis. The second model can be considered in the previous SuperHyperModel. This is SuperHyperModel. This is SuperHyperGraph but officially called “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Cancer is a disease, but the model is supposed to understand what happens in this phenomenon. The special case of this disease is considered and some parameters are used as consequences of the model. Cells are attacked by the disease, but the movement of cancer is in a specific area. Knowing

the mind of cancer can help to find some cures for this disease. SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic Super-HyperGraph are super-hypermodels used in “cancer diagnosis” and both are the foundation of the background of this scientific research. Sometimes cancer has occurred in an area full of cells, cell groups, and embedded styles. In this section, SuperHyperModel proposes based on the links of cancer movements in the form of unity styles with the formation of design and architecture officially called “Stable Sequence”, in the themes of specialized terms and common words. Particle for direct object. Applied concepts under the investigation of the motivation of this scientific research. The “SuperHyper” prefix refers to the theme of embedded styles for background discovery for SuperHyperNotions. Cancer diagnosis in long-term practice. The specific region is assigned by the model (called SuperHyperGraph) and the long cycle of movement of the cancer is determined by this scientific research. Sometimes the movement of Cancer is not easy to identify because there is certainty, uncertainty and neutrality about the movements and effects of Cancer in that region. This event leads us to choose another model [said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph]. Easy understanding of what happened and what was done. There are some specific models that are well known and named and some general models. The movements and effects of cancer in complex pathways and between complex groups of cells can be visualized by a neurosophic superhyperpath (-/SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The goal is to find Stable Sequence or Neutrosophic Stable Sequence for SuperHyperModels in it. Some general results are presented. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges, but it is not enough as having at least three SuperHyperEdges is necessary to form any style of cycle. There is no form of cycle, but it is literally a form of any cycle. It literally transforms and does not form.

Question 2.1. *How to define “SuperHyperNotions and to do research” to find the “Stable Sequence Rate” of any cell or groups of cells based on fixed cell or fixed group of cells broadly, “Stable Sequence Rate” based on fixed groups or fixed cells. Groups of groups of cells?*

Question 2.2. *What are the best descriptions for “diagnosing cancer” in terms of these chaotic and dense super-hypermodels in which embedded concepts are depicted?*

This motivation to find concepts to use in this dense model is called “SuperHyperGraphs”. So it motivates us to define different types of “Stable Sequence” and “neutrosophic Stable Sequence” over “superhypergraph” and “neutrosophic superhypergraph”. Then this scientific research has taken more motivations to define SuperHyperClasses and find some connections among this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions. It motivates us to obtain examples and examples to clarify the framework of this scientific research. The general results and some of the results about some of the connections are the ways that the key point of this scientific research, “diagnosis of cancer” is more understandable and clear.

The framework of this research is as follows. First, I will introduce the basic definitions to clarify the basics. In the “Introductions” subsection, basic definitions about SuperHyperGraphs and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are introduced and discussed in depth. Basic concepts are thoroughly explained and illustrated, and sometimes a literature review is used to make sense of what is to come in the coming sections. The main definitions and their explanations, along with some results on the new concepts, Stable Sequence and Neutrosophic Stable Sequence, are specified in the sections “Stable Sequence” and “Neutrosophic Stable Sequence”. In the concept of dealing with results and in Stable Sequence to create logic about the continuation of the scientific research, the ideas of SuperHyperUniform and Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform are introduced and as their consequences, the corresponding

SuperHyperClasses are specified to summarize the work done in this section, as “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. Going back to the core concepts, clever steps towards common concepts to extend new concepts in new frameworks, SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, in “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses” sections. There is the initial scientific research on supergeneral relations and as the final and final part of the theoretical scientific research is available in the section “General results”. Some general SuperHyperRelations are fundamental and are known as fundamental SuperHyperNotions, as in “General results” were extracted and discussed. “Stable Sequence”, “Neutrosophic Stable Sequence”, “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. There are curious questions about what has been done about SuperHyperNotions to make sense of the superiority of this scientific research and to discover the word “best” as a description and adjective of this scientific research as presented in the “Stable Sequence” section. The keyword of this scientific research was presented in the section “Applications in cancer diagnosis” with two cases and sub-sections “Case 1: Initial steps towards SuperHyperBipartite as SuperHyperModel” and “Case 2: Incremental steps towards SuperHyperMultiperdel as SuperHyper”. In the “open issues” section, there is a detailed examination and recognition of what was done in this scientific research and what happened in this scientific research in the form of “questions” and “issues” in order to understand this scientific research in an outstanding style, the advantages and limitations of this scientific research in addition to What has been done in this scientific research is stated in the “conclusion and final remarks” section.

3 Neutrosophic Preliminaries Of This Scientific Research On the Redeemed Ways

In this section, the basic material in this scientific research, is referred to [Single Valued Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.2,p.2), [Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.1,p.1), [Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.5,p.2), [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.7,p.3), [t-norm](**Ref. [1]**, Definition 2.7, p.3), and [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.7,p.3), [Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths] (**Ref. [1]**,Definition 5.3,p.7), and [Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)] (**Ref. [1]**,Definition 5.4,p.7). Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are addressed to **Ref. [1]**.

In this subsection, the basic material which is used in this scientific research, is presented. Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are elicited.

Definition 3.1 (Neutrosophic Set). (**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.1,p.1).

Let X be a **Eulerian-Path-Cut** of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x ; then the **Neutrosophic set** A (NS A) is an object having the form

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$$

where the functions $T, I, F : X \rightarrow]-0, 1^+[$ define respectively the a **truth-membership function**, an **indeterminacy-membership function**, and a **falsity-membership function** of the element $x \in X$ to the set A with the condition

$$-0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3^+.$$

The functions $T_A(x), I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ are real standard or nonstandard subsets of $]-0, 1^+[$.

Definition 3.2 (Single Valued Neutrosophic Set). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.2, p.2). 227

Let X be a Eulerian-Path-Cut of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x . A **single valued Neutrosophic set** A (SVNS A) is characterized by truth-membership function $T_A(x)$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_A(x)$, and a falsity-membership function $F_A(x)$. For each point x in X , $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in [0, 1]$. A SVNS A can be written as

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}.$$

Definition 3.3. The **degree of truth-membership**, **indeterminacy-membership** and **falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$T_A(X) = \min[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = \min[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$\text{and } F_A(X) = \min[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.4. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{ x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0 \}.$$

Definition 3.5 (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.5, p.2). 228

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where 229
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- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ; 232
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$); 233
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- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ; 235
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- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'})) : T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$); 237
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- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$); 239
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$); 240
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$); 241
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$); 242
- (ix) and the following conditions hold:

$$T'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$I'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}}$$

where $i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$. 243

Figure 1. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, $I'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, and $F'_{V'}(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the ii' 'th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Example 3.6. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic notion, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint.
- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic notion, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint.
- On the Figure (3), the SuperHyperNotion, namely, SuperHyperGirth, is up. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 .

Figure 2. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 3. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 4. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

- On the Figure (4), there's no empty SuperHyperEdge but E_3 are a loop SuperHyperEdge on $\{F\}$ and there are some SuperHyperEdges, namely, E_1 on $\{H, V_1, V_3\}$, alongside E_2 on $\{O, H, V_4, V_3\}$ and E_4, E_5 on $\{N, V_1, V_2, V_3, F\}$. 275
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- On the Figure (5), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 278
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- On the Figure (6), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 280
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- On the Figure (7), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 282
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- On the Figure (8), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 284
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- On the Figure (9), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 286
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- On the Figure (10), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 288
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- On the Figure (11), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 290
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- On the Figure (12), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 292
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- On the Figure (13), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 294
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- On the Figure (14), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 296
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- On the Figure (15), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 298
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Figure 5. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs mentioned as the SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 6. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 7. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs depicted SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 8. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with dense SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 9. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a messy SuperHyper-Modeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 10. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with highly-embedding-connected SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 11. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 12. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with highly-multiple-connected-style SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 13. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 14. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 15. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with Linearly-Connected SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 16. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 17. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a Linearly-overpacked SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

- On the Figure (16), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 300
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- On the Figure (17), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 302
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- On the Figure (18), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 304
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- On the Figure (19), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 306
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- On the Figure (20), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 308
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- On the Figure (21), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 310
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- On the Figure (22), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 312
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Definition 3.7 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). 314
 (Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3). 315

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) E_i ' and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items. 316
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- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**; 320
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**; 321

Figure 18. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 19. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 20. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 21. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 22. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**; 322
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**; 323
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- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**; 325
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- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**. 327
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If we choose different types of binary operations, then we could get hugely diverse types of general forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG). 329
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Definition 3.8 (t-norm). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3). 331

A binary operation $\otimes : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a **t-norm** if it satisfies the following for $x, y, z, w \in [0, 1]$: 332
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- (i) $1 \otimes x = x$; 334
- (ii) $x \otimes y = y \otimes x$; 335
- (iii) $x \otimes (y \otimes z) = (x \otimes y) \otimes z$; 336
- (iv) If $w \leq x$ and $y \leq z$ then $w \otimes y \leq x \otimes z$. 337

Definition 3.9. The **degree of truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership and falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$ (with respect to t-norm T_{norm}):

$$T_A(X) = T_{norm}[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = T_{norm}[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

and $F_A(X) = T_{norm}[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$

Definition 3.10. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0\}.$$

Definition 3.11. (General Forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'})) : T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$).

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, $I'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, and $F'_{V'}(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the ii' th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.12 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**;
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**;
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**;
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**;

(vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**.

This SuperHyperModel is too messy and too dense. Thus there's a need to have some restrictions and conditions on SuperHyperGraph. The special case of this SuperHyperGraph makes the patterns and regularities.

Definition 3.13. A graph is **SuperHyperUniform** if it's SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same.

To get more visions on SuperHyperUniform, the some SuperHyperClasses are introduced. It makes to have SuperHyperUniform more understandable.

Definition 3.14. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows.

- (i). It's **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions;
- (ii). it's **SuperHyperCycle** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges;
- (iii). it's **SuperHyperStar** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges;
- (iv). it's **SuperHyperBipartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (v). it's **SuperHyperMultiPartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (vi). it's **SuperHyperWheel** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex.

Example 3.15. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the notion.

Example 3.16. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is up.

Example 3.17. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is up.

Example 3.18. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is up.

Figure 23. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Associated to the Notions in the Example (3.15)

Figure 24. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (3.16)

Figure 27. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions in the Example (3.19)

Figure 28. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (3.20)

Example 3.19. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is up.

Example 3.20. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is up.

Definition 3.21. Let a pair $S = (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S . Then a sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic

SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s$$

is called a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s if either of following conditions hold:

- (i) $V_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (ii) there's a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ such that $v_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iii) there's a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ such that $V'_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iv) there's a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (v) there's a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vi) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vii) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (viii) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (ix) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$.

Definition 3.22. (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If for all $V_i, E_{j'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, $|E_{j'}| = 2$, then NSHP is called **path**;
- (ii) if for all $E_{j'}$, $|E_{j'}| = 2$, and there's V_i , $|V_i| \geq 1$, then NSHP is called **SuperPath**;
- (iii) if for all $V_i, E_{j'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, $|E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **HyperPath**;
- (iv) if there are $V_i, E_{j'}$, $|V_i| \geq 1$, $|E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath**.

Definition 3.23 (Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths).
(Ref. [1], Definition 5.3, p.7).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

have

- (i) **Neutrosophic t-strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, m, n)_{i=1}^s$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic i-strength** $(m, \min\{I(V_i)\}, n)_{i=1}^s$;

Table 1. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.27)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

(iii) **Neutrosophic f-strength** $(m, n, \min\{F(V_i)\}_{i=1}^s$; 454

(iv) **Neutrosophic strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\}_{i=1}^s$. 455

Definition 3.24 (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)). (Ref. [1], Definition 5.4, p.7). 456

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called 457
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(ix) **Neutrosophic t-connective** if $T(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic t-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 460
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(x) **Neutrosophic i-connective** if $I(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic i-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 463
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(xi) **Neutrosophic f-connective** if $F(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic f-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 466
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(xii) **Neutrosophic connective** if $(T(E), I(E), F(E)) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$. 469
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For the sake of having a Neutrosophic notion, there's a need to “**redefine**” the notion of “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. 473
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Definition 3.25. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. It's redefined **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** if the Table (1) holds. 477
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It's useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic more understandable. 479
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Definition 3.26. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. There are some **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses** if the Table (2) holds. Thus Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, notion, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite**, and **Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel** if the Table (2) holds. 482
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Table 2. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, Mentioned in the Definition (3.26)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Table 3. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.27)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of a Neutrosophic notion. Since there's more ways to get type-results to make a Neutrosophic notion more Neutrosophicly understandable.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic notion, there's a need to "redefine" the Neutrosophic notion of "Neutrosophic notion". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.27. Assume a notion. It's redefined a **Neutrosophic notion** if the Table (3) holds.

Example 3.28. Referred to the Example (3.6), assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (4).
- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (5).
- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (6).
- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (7).

Table 4. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_2	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)
V_3	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

Table 5. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.03, 0.03, 0.03)	E_2	(0, 0, 0)
V_3	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

Table 6. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.11, 0.11, 0.11)	E_2	(0, 0, 0)
V_3	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
-	-	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

Table 7. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0.08, 0.08, 0.08)
V_2	(0.11, 0.11, 0.11)	E_2	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)
V_3	(0.05, 0.05, 0.05)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.12, 0.12, 0.12)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)
$\{F\}$	(0.06, 0.06, 0.06)	E_5	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)
$\{H\}$	(0.08, 0.08, 0.08)	-	-
$\{N\}$	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	-	-
$\{O\}$	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	-	-

Figure 29. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

4 Main Resultant

Definition 4.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V'} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V'} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V'} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \min_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) | \\
 & \quad V_j \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'', \exists V_i \in V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) > (- / : \text{NOT DEFINED}) \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) > (- / : \text{NOT DEFINED}) \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'}) > (- / : \text{NOT DEFINED}) \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad \text{then } V_j \in V'', \text{ until } V'' = V_{NSHG}\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 4.2. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (29), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (8).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=1}^7\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence criteria holds.

$$|(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1}^7\}} T(V_i),$$

Figure 30. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 31. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Table 8. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	-	-
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	-	-
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Figure 32. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 33. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 34. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 35. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 36. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 37. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 38. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 42. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Table 9. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	-	-
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	-	-
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=17}\}} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=17}\}} F(V_i) \right) \\
 &= (1.82, 1.82, 1.82) = \\
 &= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left\{ \left(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i) \right) \mid \right. \\
 & \left. \text{then } V_{j=17} \in V'', \text{ then } V'' \neq V_{NSHG} \cdot \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (30), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (9). 526
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i \neq 2}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence criteria holds. 528
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i \neq 2}\}} T(V_i), \right. \\
 & \left. \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i \neq 2}\}} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i \neq 2}\}} F(V_i) \right) \\
 &= (1.56, 1.56, 1.56) = \\
 &= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left\{ \left(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i) \right) \mid \right. \\
 & \left. V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{i \neq 2}\}, \exists V_{j=2} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \right. \\
 & \left. T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 10. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	-	-
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	-	-
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 11. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	-	-
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	-	-
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

then $V_{j=2} \in V''$, then $V'' \neq V_{NSHG}$.

- On the Figure (31), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (10). 533
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i \neq 2,3}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence criteria holds. 535
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$$|(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i \neq 2,3}\}} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i \neq 2,3}\}} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i \neq 2,3}\}} F(V_i))|$$

$$= (1.32, 1.32, 1.32) =$$

$$= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i))|$$

$V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{i \neq 2,3}\}, \exists V_{j=2,3} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' :$

$$T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

then $V_{j=2,3} \in V''$, then $V'' \neq V_{NSHG}$.

- On the Figure (32), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (11). 540
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet 542
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Table 12. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	-	-
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	-	-
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$V' = \{V_{i \neq 2,3,4}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
& |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i \neq 2,3,4}\}} T(V_i), \\
& \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i \neq 2,3,4}\}} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i \neq 2,3,4}\}} F(V_i))| \\
& = (1.08, 1.08, 1.08) = \\
& = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |\{(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) | \\
& V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{i \neq 2,3,4}\}, \exists V_{j=2,3,4} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
& T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \text{then } V_{j=2,3,4} \in V'', \text{ then } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}. \}
\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (33), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (12).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=1,6,7}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
& |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,6,7}\}} T(V_i), \\
& \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,6,7}\}} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,6,7}\}} F(V_i))| \\
& = (0.78, 0.78, 0.78) = \\
& = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |\{(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) | \\
& V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{i=1,6,7}\}, \exists V_{j=2,3,4,5} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
& T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \text{then } V_{j=2,3,4,5} \in V'', \text{ then } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}. \}
\end{aligned}$$

Table 13. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	-	-
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	-	-
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 14. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	-	-
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	-	-
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

- On the Figure (34), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (13). 554
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=1,7}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence criteria holds. 556
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,7}\}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,7}\}} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,7}\}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (0.52, 0.52, 0.52) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |\{(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) | \\
 & V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{i=1,7}\}, \exists V_{j=2-6} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \text{then } V_{j=2-6} \in V'', \text{ then } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}. \}
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (35), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (14). 561
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=1}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence criteria holds. 563
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$$|(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1}\}} T(V_i),$$

Table 15. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=3-7}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1}\}} I(V_i), \quad \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1}\}} F(V_i) \\
 &= (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) = \\
 &= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} | \{ (\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) | \\
 & \quad V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{i=1}\}, \exists V_{j=2-7} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad \text{then } V_{j=2-7} \in V'', \text{ then } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}. \}
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 4.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (36), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (15).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=1,8,12,16,20,25,32}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & | (\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,8,12,16,20,25,32}\}} T(V_i), \\
 & \quad \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,8,12,16,20,25,32}\}} I(V_i), \quad \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,8,12,16,20,25,32}\}} F(V_i)) | \\
 &= (1.82, 1.82, 1.82) = \\
 &= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} | \{ (\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) | \\
 & \quad V_{i=12} \in V'' = \{V_{1,8,12,16,20,25,32}\}, \exists V_{j=2,11,15,19,24} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad \text{then } V_{j=11,15,19,24} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\
 & \quad V_{i=8} \in V'' = \{V_{1,8,11,12,15,16,19,20,24,25,32}\}, \exists V_{j \neq 2,11,15,19,24} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 16. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$F'_V(E_{i'}) (V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

then $V_{j \neq 2, 11, 15, 19, 24} \in V''$, then $V'' = V_{NSHG}$ }

- On the Figure (37), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (16). 577
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=1,8,12,16,20,25,32}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence criteria holds. 579
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$$\begin{aligned} & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,8,12,16,20,25,32}\}} T(V_i), \\ & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,8,12,16,20,25,32}\}} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,8,12,16,20,25,32}\}} F(V_i))| \\ & = (1.82, 1.82, 1.82) = \end{aligned}$$

$$= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i))|$$

$$V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{1,8,12,16,20,25,32}\}, \exists V_{j=2,11,15,19,24} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' :$$

$$T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$F'_V(E_{i'}) (V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

then $V_{j=11,15,19,24} \in V''$, but $V'' \neq V_{NSHG}$,

$$V_{i=8} \in V'' = \{V_{1,8,11,12,15,16,19,20,24,25,32}\}, \exists V_{j \neq 2, 11, 15, 19, 24} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' :$$

$$T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$F'_V(E_{i'}) (V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

then $V_{j \neq 2, 11, 15, 19, 24} \in V''$, then $V'' = V_{NSHG}$ }

- On the Figure (38), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (17). 584
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=1,3,8,12,16,20,25,32}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence criteria holds. 586
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$$\begin{aligned} & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,8,12,16,20,25,32}\}} T(V_i), \\ & \end{aligned}$$

Table 17. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 18. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,8,12,16,20,25,32}\}} I(V_i), \quad \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,8,12,16,20,25,32}\}} F(V_i) \\
 & = (2.08, 2.08, 2.08) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} | \{ (\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) \} \\
 & \quad V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{1,3,8,12,16,20,25,32}\}, \exists V_{j=2,11,15,19,24} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad \text{then } V_{j=2,11,15,19,24} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\
 & \quad V_{i=3} \in V'' = \{V_{1-3,8,11,12,15,16,19,20,24,25,32}\}, \exists V_{j=8-10,31} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad \text{then } V_{j=8-10,31} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\
 & \quad V_{i=8} \in V'' = \{V_{1-3,8-12,15,16,19,20,24,25,31,32}\}, \exists V_{j \neq 2,8-11,15,19,24,31} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad \text{then } V_{j \neq 2,8-11,15,19,24,31} \in V'', \text{ then } V'' = V_{NSHG}. \}
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (39), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (18). 591
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=1,3,8,16,20,25,32}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and 593
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Table 19. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence criteria holds.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,8,16,20,25,32}\}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,8,16,20,25,32}\}} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,8,16,20,25,32}\}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (1.82, 1.82, 1.82) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i))| \\
 & \quad V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{1,3,8,12,16,20,25,32}\}, \exists V_{j=2,11,15,19,24} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad \text{then } V_{j=2,11,15,19,24} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\
 & \quad V_{i=3} \in V'' = \{V_{1-3,8,11,12,15,16,19,20,24,25,32}\}, \exists V_{j=4,8-10,12-14,31} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad \text{then } V_{j=4,8-10,12-14,31} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\
 & \quad V_{i=8} \in V'' = \{V_{1-4,8-15,16,19,20,24,25,31,32}\}, \exists V_{j \neq 2,8-11,15,19,24,31} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad \text{then } V_{j \neq 2,8-11,15,19,24,31} \in V'', \text{ then } V'' = V_{NSHG}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (40), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (19).

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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5,20,25,32}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence criteria holds.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5,20,25,32}\}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5,8,16,20,25,32}\}} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5,8,16,20,25,32}\}} F(V_i))|
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 20. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$= (1.3, 1.3, 1.3) =$$

$$= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i) \right) \right|$$

$$V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{1,3,5,12,20,25,32}\}, \exists V_{j=2,11,15,19,24} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' :$$

$$T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

then $V_{j=2,11,15,19,24} \in V''$, but $V'' \neq V_{NSHG}$,

$$V_{i=3} \in V'' = \{V_{1-3,5,11,12,15,19,20,24,25,32}\}, \exists V_{j=4,8-10,12-14,31} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' :$$

$$T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

then $V_{j=4,8-10,12-14,31} \in V''$, but $V'' \neq V_{NSHG}$,

$$V_{i=5} \in V'' = \{V_{1-5,8-15,19,20,24,25,31,32}\}, \exists V_{j=16-18} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' :$$

$$T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

then $V_{j=16-18} \in V''$, but $V'' \neq V_{NSHG}$,

$$V_{i=8} \in V'' = \{V_{1-5,8-15,16-19,20,24,25,31,32}\}, \exists V_{j \neq 2,8-11,15,19,24,31} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' :$$

$$T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

then $V_{j \neq 2,8-11,15,19,24,31} \in V''$, then $V'' = V_{NSHG}$.

- On the Figure (41), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (20).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5,25,32}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence criteria holds.

$$\left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5,25,32}\}} T(V_i), \right. \right.$$

Table 21. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5,25,32}\}} I(V_i), \quad \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5,25,32}\}} F(V_i) \\
 &= (0.78, 0.78, 0.78) = \\
 &= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i) \right) \right| \\
 & \quad V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{1,3,5,25,32}\}, \exists V_{j=2,11,15,19,24} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \text{then } V_{j=2,11,15,19,24} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\
 & \quad V_{i=3} \in V'' = \{V_{1-3,5,11,15,19,24,25,32}\}, \exists V_{j=4,8-10,12-14,31} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \text{then } V_{j=4,8-10,12-14,31} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG},
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \quad V_{i=5} \in V'' = \{V_{1-5,8-15,19,24,25,31,32}\}, \exists V_{j=6,16-18,20-23} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \text{then } V_{j=1-5,8-15,19,24,25,31,32} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\
 & \quad V_{i=8} \in V'' = \{V_{1-5,8-15,16-19,20,24,25,31,32}\}, \exists V_{j \neq 2,8-11,15,19,24,31} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \text{then } V_{j \neq 2,8-11,15,19,24,31} \in V'', \text{ then } V'' = V_{NSHG}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (42), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (21).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5,7}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is

called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
& |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5,7}\}} T(V_i), \\
& \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5,7}\}} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5,7}\}} F(V_i))| \\
& = (0.52, 0.52, 0.52) = \\
& = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i))| \\
& \quad V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{1,3,5,7}\}, \exists V_{j=2,11,15,19,24} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
& \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad \text{then } V_{j=2,11,15,19,24} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\
& \quad V_{i=3} \in V'' = \{V_{1-3,5,7,11,15,19,24}\}, \exists V_{j=4,8-10,12-14,31} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
& \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad \text{then } V_{j=4,8-10,12-14,31} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\
& \quad V_{i=5} \in V'' = \{V_{1-5,7-15,19,24,31}\}, \exists V_{j=6,16-18,20-23} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
& \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad \text{then } V_{j=6,16-18,20-23} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\
& \quad V_{i=7} \in V'' = \{V_{1-24,31}\}, \exists V_{j=25-30,32-34} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
& \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad \text{then } V_{j=25-30,32-34} \in V'', \text{ then } V'' = V_{NSHG}.
\end{aligned}$$

5 Main Result

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Theorem 5.1. (Main Result and Main Theorem).

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Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite has the letter z . The notion on the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite and Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath coincide.

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Proof.

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(i). Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{P_1}, E_1, \\
& V_1^{P_1}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_1}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_1}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. 626

There's a new way to redefine as 627

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is 628
corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence. 629
The latter is straightforward. 630

(ii). Let 631

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperStable Sequence taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath 633
 $ESHC : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 634

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is 635
corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence. 636
The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable 637
Sequence. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on 638
Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence could be applied. The unique embedded 639
Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence proposes some longest Neutrosophic 640
SuperHyperStable Sequence excerpt from some representatives. The latter is 641
straightforward. 642

Proposition 5.2. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHM$ be a pair 643
 $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The 644
Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence set is as follows.*

$$\{V^{P_1}\}.$$

Proof. Let 645

$$P :$$

$$V_1^{P_1}, E_1,$$

$$V_2^{P_1}, E_2$$

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$$P :$$

$$V_1^{P_1}, E_1,$$

$$V_2^{P_1}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

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$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence.
The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Proposition 5.3. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHM$ be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence number is as follows.*

$$|V^{P_1}| \times 0.26.$$

Proof. Let

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$$P :$$

$$V_1^{P_1}, E_1,$$

$$V_1^{P_1}, E_2$$

651

$$P :$$

$$V_1^{P_i}, E_1,$$

$$V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

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$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence.
The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Proposition 5.4. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath ($ESHG$) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence set is as follows.*

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$$\{$$

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL},$$

$$V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, \dots$$

$$\}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperStable Sequence taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.5. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (ESHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence number is as follows.*

$$\frac{|V|}{2} \times 0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperStable Sequence taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence.

The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Definition 5.6. (Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite and Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath).

- (i). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Every pair of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices has the same maximum letter, i.e., Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices mutually has the same maximum letter. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$ is called **Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite**.
- (ii). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Every pair of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices has the same maximum letter, i.e., Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices mutually has the same maximum letter. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$ is called **Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath**.

Proposition 5.7. Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHM$ be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence set is as follows.

$$\{V^{P_1}\}.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_1}, E_1, \\ V_2^{P_1}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_1}, E_1, \\ V_2^{P_1}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.8. Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHM$ be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence number is as follows.

$$|V^{P_1}| \times 0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_1}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_1}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_1}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_1}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.9. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (ESHC) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence set is as follows.*

$$\{ \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, \dots \\ \}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperStable Sequence taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHC : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on

Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.10. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (ESHC) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence number is as follows.*

$$\frac{|V|}{2} \times 0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperStable Sequence taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHC : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.11. *(Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite and Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath).*

- (i). *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, from different SuperHyperParts, have the maximum letter. Then the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices don't have the same maximum letter, are in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence set.*
- (ii). *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic EXTERNAL SuperHyperVertices with distance two have the maximum letter. Then the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices don't have the same maximum letter, are in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence set.*

Proof.

(i). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence.
The latter is straightforward.

(ii). Let

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperStable Sequence taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath
 $ESHC : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence.
The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable
Sequence. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on
Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence could be applied. The unique embedded
Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence proposes some longest Neutrosophic
SuperHyperStable Sequence excerpt from some representatives. The latter is
straightforward. □

Proposition 5.12. (Embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite and Embedded
Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath).

(i). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, from different SuperHyperParts, is in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence set. 768
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(ii). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then every Neutrosophic EXTERNAL SuperHyperVertices with distance two is in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence set. 771
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Proof. 774

(i). Let 775

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 777
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$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence. The latter is straightforward. 779
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(ii). Let 782

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperStable Sequence taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHC : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 784
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$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. 786
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6 Neutrosophic Applications in Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition

The cancer is the Neutrosophic disease but the Neutrosophic model is going to figure out what's going on this Neutrosophic phenomenon. The special Neutrosophic case of this Neutrosophic disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer could help to find some Neutrosophic treatments for this Neutrosophic disease.

In the following, some Neutrosophic steps are Neutrosophic devised on this disease.

Step 1. (Neutrosophic Definition) The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer in the long-term Neutrosophic function.

Step 2. (Neutrosophic Issue) The specific region has been assigned by the Neutrosophic model [it's called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] and the long Neutrosophic cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done.

Step 3. (Neutrosophic Model) There are some specific Neutrosophic models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some general Neutrosophic models. The moves and the Neutrosophic traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable Sequence, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence or the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence in those Neutrosophic Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels.

7 Case 1: The Initial Neutrosophic Steps Toward Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite as Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Neutrosophic Solution) In the Neutrosophic Figure (43), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured.

By using the Neutrosophic Figure (43) and the Table (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite is obtained.

The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESH B : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (43), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence.

Figure 44. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence

Table 23. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyper-Edges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

8 Case 2: The Increasing Neutrosophic Steps Toward Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite as Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Neutrosophic Solution) In the Neutrosophic Figure (44), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. By using the Neutrosophic Figure (44) and the Table (23), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is obtained. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (44), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence.

9 Wondering Open Problems But As The Directions To Forming The Motivations

In what follows, some “problems” and some “questions” are proposed. The SuperHyperStable Sequence and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence are defined on a real-world application, titled “Cancer’s Recognitions”.

Question 9.1. Which the else SuperHyperModels could be defined based on Cancer’s

recognitions?

Question 9.2. *Are there some SuperHyperNotions related to SuperHyperStable Sequence and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence?*

Question 9.3. *Are there some Algorithms to be defined on the SuperHyperModels to compute them?*

Question 9.4. *Which the SuperHyperNotions are related to beyond the SuperHyperStable Sequence and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence?*

Problem 9.5. *The SuperHyperStable Sequence and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable Sequence do a SuperHyperModel for the Cancer's recognitions and they're based on SuperHyperStable Sequence, are there else?*

Problem 9.6. *Which the fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are related to these SuperHyperNumbers types-results?*

Problem 9.7. *What's the independent research based on Cancer's recognitions concerning the multiple types of SuperHyperNotions?*

10 Conclusion and Closing Remarks

In this section, closing and concluding remarks are presented. The drawbacks of this scientific research are shown. Some advantages and disadvantages of this scientific research are highlighted.

This scientific research uses some approaches to further understand the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs. In this effort, two SuperHyperNotions are defined on the Stable Sequence. For this reason, in the second definition, the original definition of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is redefined on the position of the alphabets. Based on the new Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph definition, the new SuperHyperNotion, Neutrosophic Stable Sequence, finds a suitable background to implement some results on. Some SuperHyperClasses and some Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses are the subjects of this scientific research on modeling areas that are subject to cancer attacks in order to recognize this disease as mentioned under the title "Cancer Diagnosis". To formalize the SuperHyperNotion, Stable Sequence, SuperHyperClasses and new SuperHyperClasses instances are introduced. Some general results are summarized in the Stable Sequence and Neutrosophic Stable Sequence sections. Clarifications, examples, and literature reviews go all the way. In this scientific research, the literature review has met the lines containing concepts and results. SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are super-hypermodels in "cancer diagnosis" and both are the foundation of the background of this scientific research. Sometimes cancer has occurred in an area full of cells, cell groups, and embedded styles. In this section, SuperHyperModel proposes SuperHyperNotions, formally called "Stable Sequence", based on the connections of Cancer's movements in the longest and strongest styles with the formation of design and architecture, in terms of terms and whispering words. . The "SuperHyper" prefix refers to the topic of embedded styles to explore the background of SuperHyperNotions. In the table (24), the advantages and ways of this scientific research are specified, pointed out and expressed.

11 Background

There are some scientific researches covering the topic of this scientific research. In what follows, there are some discussion and literature reviews about them.

Table 24. A look at this scientific research and beyond

Advantages	Limitations
1. Redefining the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph	1. General Results
2. Stable Sequence	
3. Neutrosophic Stable Sequence	2. Other SuperHyperNumbers
4. modeling cancer diagnoses	
5. SuperHyperClasses	3. SuperHyperFamilies

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot*” in **Ref. [1]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms with introducing used neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Current Trends in Mass Communication (CTMC)*” with ISO abbreviation “*Curr Trends Mass Comm*” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 32-55.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*” in **Ref. [2]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer’s Treatments. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*” with ISO abbreviation “*J Math Techniques Comput Math*” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 35-47. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*A Research on Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic Super Hypergraph by Eulerian Super Hyper Cycles and Hamiltonian Sets as Hyper Covering Versus Super separations*” in **Ref. [3]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer’s Recognition. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*” with ISO abbreviation “*J Math Techniques Comput Math*” in volume 2 and issue 3 with pages 136-148. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction to Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Beyond*” in **Ref. [4]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*” with ISO abbreviation “*J Math Techniques Comput Math*” in volume 2 and issue 6 with pages 221-307. The research article studies

deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. 935
It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and 936
fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is 937
titled “*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph by* 938
Initial Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Initial Eulogy on Super Initial EULA” in **Ref. [5]** by 939
Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on 940
SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental 941
SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic 942
SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled 943
“*International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research*” with ISO 944
abbreviation “*IJPAMR*” in volume 3 and issue 2 with pages 60-88 and doi: 945
10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.60-88. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is 946
titled “*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by* 947
Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut” in **Ref. [6]** by 948
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SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental 950
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SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled 952
“*International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research*” with ISO 953
abbreviation “*IJPAMR*” in volume 3 and issue 2 with pages 102-124 and doi: 954
10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.102-124. The research article studies deeply with choosing 955
directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough 956
toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental 957
SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*Super* 958
Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and 959
Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes” in **Ref. [7]** by 960
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SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Journal* 964
of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)” with ISO 965
abbreviation “*J Math Techniques Comput Math*” in volume 1 and issue 3 with pages 966
242-263. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic 967
SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent 968
results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal 969
paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*neutrosophic co-degree and neutrosophic* 970
degree alongside chromatic numbers in the setting of some classes related to neutrosophic 971
hypergraphs” in **Ref. [8]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel 972
approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph 973
based on general forms without using neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic 974
SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Journal* 975
of Current Trends in Computer Science Research (JCTCSR)” with ISO abbreviation “*J* 976
Curr Trends Comp Sci Res” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 16-24. The research 977
article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic 978
SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial 979
background. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic 980
hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward 981
independent results based on initial background. In some articles are titled “*0039 —* 982
Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring 983
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Some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [396]** by Henry Garrett (2023) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 5679 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs” and published by Dr. Henry Garrett. This research book covers different types of notions and settings in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory.

Also, some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [397]** by Henry Garrett (2023) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 6667 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “Neutrosophic Duality” and published by Dr. Henry Garrett. This research book presents different types of notions SuperHyperResolving and SuperHyperDominating in the setting of duality in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory. This research book has scrutiny on the complement of the intended set and the intended set, simultaneously. It’s smart to consider a set but acting on its complement that what’s done in this research book which is popular in the terms of high readers in Scribd.

See the seminal scientific researches [1–3]. The formalization of the notions on the framework of notions in SuperHyperGraphs, Neutrosophic notions in SuperHyperGraphs theory, and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs theory at [4–257] alongside scientific research books at [258–395]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd ,in the terms of high readers, 5679 and 6667 respectively, on neutrosophic

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